

SHORT SURVEY ON UNCERTAINTY IN SELF-ADAPTIVE SYSTEMS

Question 1 - Self-adapting systems can deal only with anticipated changes. Self-adapting systems cannot deal with unanticipated changes.

- Agree
- Disagree

Please explain your answer:

Question 2 - If you selected “Disagree” as answer for Question 1, please explain how the system may be able to gain awareness of the occurrence of a change that it was not engineered to anticipate:

Assuming that the Knowledge a self-adaptive system collects and generates (about the system it manages and its environment) is represented as a runtime model, then:

Question 3 - Uncertainties in such a model can be associated with (*select all that apply*):

- 1. The parameters in the model
- 2. The structure of the model
- 3. The modeling formalism that cannot capture the relevant aspects of the system

Other (*please specify*):

If you have not selected ALL the options 1, 2, or 3 to Question 3, please explain why:

Question 4 - Uncertainties in the values of model parameters can be dealt with by expressing them using (*select all that apply*):

- Concrete values (estimated at design time, or determined at runtime)
- Intervals of values
- Probabilities and probability distributions
- Combination of intervals and probabilities (e.g., confidence intervals)

Other (*please specify*):

Question 5 - Uncertainties in the model structure (i.e., elements in the model or parts of the model) can be handled by (*select all that apply*):

- Using multiple models and applying:
 - Model averaging (combining several models into one model)
 - Model selection (selecting one model among different models based on some criteria)
- Alternative structures within a model with associated probabilities

Other (*please specify*):

Question 6 - When the uncertainty comes from the modeling formalism that does not allow capturing all relevant aspects of the system, it is not possible to handle this uncertainty at runtime:

- Agree
- Disagree

If disagree, why?

Question 7 - Handling uncertainty in safety-critical self-adaptive systems (e.g., self-driving cars) is difficult because of remaining open challenges associated with (*select all that apply*):

- Providing assurances that self-adaptation decisions are correct with respect to the specified goals
- Making the self-adaptation proactive instead of reactive
- Integrating machine learning into the self-adaptation process
- Ensuring the scalability of the self-adaptation

Other (*please specify*):

THANK YOU FOR YOUR COLLABORATION!

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